

JOB SATISFACTION LEVELS OF VOLLEYBALL REFEREES SERVING AT TURKISH 1ST, 2ND AND 3RD LEAGUES (ISTANBUL SAMPLE)

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Abstract:

Job satisfaction is defined as the result of individuals' attitudes towards their jobs, which is affected by such factors as job related wage, supervision, working conditions, improvements opportunities, acknowledgement of skills, job evaluation, human relations in the organization and environment. It is the most important problem of human resources in every area, from public sector to private sector, industry to sports, teachers to officers, athletes to referees. Job satisfaction has social, economic and psychological consequences on individuals. The purpose of the present research is studying the job satisfaction levels of volleyball referees as one of the human resources sports sector. The universe of the research consists of referees working for Turkish Volleyball Federation, while the sample consists of 134 volleyball referees selected via simple sampling method among the universe. Job Satisfaction of the participants was evaluated with "Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ)" short form. At the first step, Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) scores of participants were calculated. With these scores, referees' satisfaction levels from external and internal environment factors were determined. At the second step, variation in these scores by gender was analysed. Non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test was utilized at 0.05 significance level, to analyse the variation in average scores from job satisfaction factors. The findings of the present research are as follows: General job satisfaction of volleyball referees ranges between 3.73 and neutral satisfaction level, increasing towards satisfaction level. This is a positive development for Volleyball Federation. For the

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institutions to survive and compete, they need to use the resources they have efficiently and increase their general performance accordingly. Average satisfaction score of referees from internal environmental conditions is 3.9200 and the average satisfaction from external environmental conditions is 3.3582. This finding indicates that referees are more satisfied with the refereeing job than they are with the opportunities provided by the federation.

Keywords: job satisfaction, volleyball referee, refereeing, professional conditions

1. Introduction

Today, organizational culture and organizational culture are among the most important concepts in organizations -either profit or non-profit- that exhibit product based management style. An organization is expected to form an organizational culture and sustain this. Organizational culture, which is formed by the employees during the production of the targeted product, can affect the product both positively and negatively. Job satisfaction is a tool for regulating these two concepts and therefore the product optimally for organizational administrators.

First systematic studies on job satisfaction started in 1930s. Since then, more than 3000 studies have been conducted on this subject matter. There are two reasons for job satisfaction studies; first satisfaction needs to be studied for organizations due its effects on job-related behaviours. Second, satisfaction can increase the productivity for individuals. Therefore, factors affecting job satisfaction must be studied and detected to increase the productivity for both the organizations and the individuals (O'Driscoll, 1996).

Job satisfaction is a reaction of the employees towards their jobs and organizations (Pugh et al., 1991). Additionally, job satisfaction is considered as the rate of the outcomes employees gain from the organization in return for their contributions to the organization (Schuler and Huber, 1985). It is about the values individuals have, and the pleasure they take in their jobs (Tortop et al., 1993). It is individuals' attitudes towards their jobs (Gencay, 1997). Job satisfaction is employees' reaction to their roles in their jobs (Unsal, 2005). Job satisfaction is resulted from positive or negative feelings employees experience in their job behaviours and organizational environment. These feelings are resulted from internal and external resources. Internal resources of satisfaction are internal awards. Doing a job they like provides individuals with sense of satisfaction. External resources are motivators in the organization (Ersen, 1997). Various factors affecting the content of job satisfaction and the concepts of balance,

equality and favour resulting from these, form the job satisfaction. If individuals consider their jobs consistent with these concepts for themselves and other, they find their jobs satisfying for themselves and other. If they can't associate their jobs with concepts of balance and equality, they experience dissatisfaction (Knopp. 1995). Job satisfaction is being content or discontent with one's jobs. Sense of satisfaction only occurs when the requirements of the job match the qualities of the employees (Bingol. 1997).

Job satisfaction studies mostly focuses on demographic variables, such as age, gender, educational background and seniority. Individuals need to get to know their working environment, get used to it, have a positive climate for themselves in order to commit to their jobs, and all these require some time. Working habits and commitment levels of young people may be less strong as they can find more interesting or attractive things to do in their lives. Since middle-aged would be more familiar with their jobs, job environment, it would be easier for them to understand the satisfaction they feel. Older people resist more to change as they get older, which results in less willingness to use technology, less ambition, and less resistance to unhealthy and stressed environments (Pitss. 1995). Social roles given to women and men affect their behaviours in their work places, and present a very important factor for their perspectives of their jobs. As the level of education gets better, individuals' expectations from their working life and their jobs vary. Individuals conduct their educational intended for a certain profession with the effects of their environment, socio-economic conditions and family structure. Considering that individuals, who cannot feel satisfaction from their jobs, tend to quit, seniority and job satisfaction are correlated concepts.

Productivity at work and professional attitude are also associated with job satisfaction. It is natural that positive attitudes towards work are correlated with positive outcomes in terms of quality, yet studies conducted so far didn't come up with such findings. There are employees with job satisfaction but no high productivity. The question of whether job satisfaction increases productivity or high productivity results in satisfaction is another aspect of the subject matter. The reason for the ambiguity of the relationship between job satisfaction and productivity can be the existence of awards. Job satisfaction is generally more the result than the reason of productivity, since high productivity brings along awards, such as increase in wage, reputation and promotion, which provides job satisfaction (Wroom. 1964).

As is known, job satisfaction can be the attitude towards either the job as a whole or some aspects or features of the job. Satisfaction from each factor, such as organization and relations within, motivation and the appropriate working environment, career planning, success evaluation and wage management forms the job satisfaction as a

whole. Low job satisfaction refers to the low levels of meeting of these expectations. Yet, employees can still be dissatisfied with some aspects of their jobs.

Referees, who serve as a bridge between the spectators and also between the opposing teams, and evaluate the game in accordance with pre-determined rules, must be model individuals with their living, personality, knowledge of human psychology and social sociology, and behaviours inside and outside the court (Dogan. 2004). Knowledge of game rules isn't enough to be a good referee. Besides the knowledge of rules, passion of refereeing, sense of responsibility, well competition management skills, fair management, quick and good decision-making, courageous management style, and morally high personality are features good referees should have (Akcil. 1996). Referees have to exhibit all competency, experience and positive psychological behaviours required by the modern sport to increase the pleasure taken in the game by spectators and players. Referees must be individuals, who do less mistakes both in their professional and private lives, have a certain job and profession, can express their opinions openly even when they know that the consequences can be against them, have no prejudices during the competitions, manage the games in a way to earn managers and spectators' respect behave equally for both sides, and believe there is no place for colours and flags in sports (Savucu et al.. 2008). Turkish referees mostly do refereeing as a second job. Accordingly, refereeing isn't considered as a profession in Turkey (Karakucuk and Ermihan. 1996).

Referees can be exposed to many ugly and unfair words or acts. But why do they endure this? Is it the money or the fame? There have been no referees managing both of these yet. According to Day (1996), the answer to this question can only be the sickly passion and pleasure doing this job. The present research is important in terms of providing a source of feedback for managers on the evaluation of internal and external environmental factors affecting job satisfaction levels of referees serving for Turkish Volleyball Federation.

2. Material and Method

The present research on the job satisfaction levels of volleyball referees of Turkish Volleyball Federation is designed in accordance with descriptive research model. The research utilized "Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ)" Short Form to collect data. Validity and reliability studies of MSQ short form were conducted by Gillet and Schwap (Eksi. 2000). According to the findings of the present research, validity of the questionnaire form is 0.83.

The universe of the research consists of referees working for Turkish Volleyball Federation, while the sample consists of 134 volleyball referees selected via simple sampling method among the universe. At the first step, Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) scores of participants were calculated. With these score, referees' satisfaction levels from external and internal environment factors were determined. At the second step, variation in these scores by gender was analysed. Non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test was utilized at 0.05 significance level, to analyse the variation in average scores from job satisfaction factors.

3. Findings

Most of the referees, who participated in the present research, were within 20-30 age range (57.5%). 22.4% were in 31-40 range. Of the participants, 73.1% were male and 26.9% were female. According to the collected data. 48.5% of the participants had been refereeing for 5 years or more. 64.9% had bachelor degrees but only 20.1% of these were graduates of Schools of Physical Education and Sports. 44.8% of the participants worked as public servants, 6.7% as labourer, 11.9% were self-employed, 36.6% marked the other option.

Table 1: On account of enabling a constant job for me

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Not satisfied at all	10	7.5	7.6	7.6
Not satisfied	19	14.2	14.4	22.0
Not sure	46	34.3	34.8	56.8
Satisfied	42	31.3	31.8	88.6
Very satisfied	15	11.2	11.4	100.0
Total	132	98.5	100.0	

As presented in Table 1, 34.3% of the participants were undecided in terms of refereeing providing a constant job, 31.3% stated they were satisfied.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Not satisfied at all	76	56.7	56.7	56.7
Not satisfied	20	14.9	14.9	71.6
Not sure	19	14.2	14.2	85.8
Satisfied	12	9.0	9.0	94.8
Very satisfied	7	5.2	5.2	100.0
Total	134	100.0	100.0	

As presented in Table 2, 56.7% of the participants weren't satisfied at all with the wage they earned from refereeing.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Not satisfied at all	3	2.2	2.2	2.2
Not satisfied	17	12.7	12.7	14.9
Not sure	17	12.7	12.7	27.6
Satisfied	62	46.3	46.3	73.9
Very satisfied	35	26.1	26.1	100.0
Total	134	100.0	100.0	

As presented in Table 3, 46.3% of the participants were satisfied with refereeing in terms of the possibility of uplift, while 26.1% were very satisfied.

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Not satisfied at all	12	9.0	9.0	9.0
Not satisfied	34	25.4	25.4	34.3
Not sure	33	24.6	24.6	59.0
Satisfied	45	33.6	33.6	92.5
Very satisfied	10	7.5	7.5	100.0
Total	134	100.0	100.0	

As presented in Table 4, 33.6% of the participants were satisfied with refereeing in terms of the working conditions, while 25.4% were satisfied and 24.6% were undecided.

Table 5: The comparison of average values of job satisfaction judgements of referees from internal environmental conditions

Job Satisfaction Judgements	μ
Being able to keep busy all the time	3.5224
The chance to work alone on the job	3.6667
The chance to do different things from time to time	4.3158
The chance to be somebody in the community	4.2030
Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience	3.6870
The way my job provides for steady employment	3.2500
The chance to do things for other people	4.1045
The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	4.2836
The chance to try my own skills of doing refereeing	4.0448
The way my co-referees get along with each other	3.8433
The praise I get for doing a good refereeing job	3.9701
The feeling of accomplishment I get from refereeing	4.1493
General Average Value	3.9200

As presented in Table 5 the average score of the level of satisfaction referees have from internal environmental conditions is 3.92. In terms of their internal dynamics, referees are very close to the satisfaction level.

Table 6: The comparison of average values of job satisfaction judgements of referees from external environmental conditions

Job Satisfaction Judgements	μ
The chance to tell my referee friends what to do	3.7463
The way refereeing related decisions are put into practice	3.7463
My pay and the amount of refereeing I do	1.9104
The chances for advancement on refereeing	3.8134
The working conditions	3.0522
The freedom to use my own judgment	3.8806
General Average Value	3.3582

As presented in Table 6, the average score of the level of satisfaction referees have from external environmental conditions is 3.3582. In terms of external environmental conditions dynamics, referees are at neutral satisfaction level.

Table 7: Gender and job satisfaction levels of the referees for the Mann-Whitney U Test

	Gender	N	Mean Rank
Being able to keep busy all the time	Male	98	65.04
	Female	35	72.50
	Total	133	
The chance to work alone on the job	Male	96	62.59
	Female	35	75.34
	Total	131	
The chance to do different things from time to time	Male	97	66.30
	Female	35	67.04
	Total	132	
The chance to be somebody in the community	Male	97	63.64
	Female	35	74.43
	Total	132	
Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience	Male	96	63.16
	Female	34	72.10
	Total	130	
The way my job provides for steady employment	Male	96	60.99
	Female	35	79.74
	Total	131	
The chance to do things for other people	Male	98	67.65
	Female	35	65.19
	Total	133	
The chance to tell my referee friends what to do	Male	98	68.89
	Female	35	61.71
	Total	133	
The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	Male	98	67.48
	Female	35	65.66
	Total	133	
The way refereeing related decisions are put into practice	Male	98	69.50
	Female	35	60.00
	Total	133	
My pay and the amount of refereeing I do	Male	98	66.68
	Female	35	67.90
	Total	133	
The chances for advancement on refereeing	Male	98	67.67
	Female	35	65.11

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	Total	133	
The freedom to use my own judgment	Male	98	68.40
	Female	35	63.07
	Total	133	
The chance to try my own skills of doing refereeing	Male	98	69.78
	Female	35	59.23
	Total	133	
The working conditions	Male	98	65.70
	Female	35	70.64
	Total	133	
The way my co-referees get along with each other	Male	98	64.66
	Female	35	73.54
	Total	133	
The praise I get for doing a good refereeing job	Male	98	67.31
	Female	35	66.13
	Total	133	
The feeling of accomplishment I get from refereeing	Male	98	67.96
	Female	35	64.31
	Total	133	
How long have you been working as a referee?	Male	98	69.94
	Female	35	58.77
	Total	133	

Test Statistics ^a

	Being able to keep busy all the time	The chance to work alone on the job	The chance to do different things from time to time	The chance to be somebody in the community
Mann-Whitney U	1522.500	1353.000	1678.500	1420.000
Wilcoxon W	6373.500	6009.000	6431.500	6173.000
Z	-1.075	-1.843	-.109	-1.552
p	.283	.065	.913	.121

a. **Group Variable:** Gender

Test Statistics ^a

	Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience	The way my job provides for steady employment	The chance to do things for other people	The chance to tell my referee friends what to do
Mann-Whitney U	1407.500	1199.000	1651.500	1530.000
Wilcoxon W	6063.500	5855.000	2281.500	2160.000
Z	-1.246	-2.606	-.356	-1.022
P	.213	.009	.722	.307

a. Group Variable: Gender

Test Statistics ^a

	The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	The way refereeing related decisions are put into practice	My pay and the amount of refereeing I do	The chances for advancement on refereeing
Mann-Whitney U	1668.000	1470.000	1683.500	1649.000
Wilcoxon W	2298.000	2100.000	6534.500	2279.000
Z	-.265	-1.344	-.179	-.360
P	.791	.179	.858	.719

a. Group Variable: Gender

Test Statistics ^a

	The freedom to use my own judgment	The chance to try my own skills of doing refereeing	The working conditions	The way my co-referees get along with each other
Mann-Whitney U	1577.500	1443.000	1587.500	1486.000
Wilcoxon W	2207.500	2073.000	6438.500	6337.000
Z	-.799	-1.507	-.676	-1.262
P	.424	.132	.499	.207

a. Group Variable: Gender

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Human beings have to work to survive. However, some people need to do an extra job. Refereeing in various branches of sport provides both employed and unemployed (students, etc.) individuals with income. Effective use of this time is related with the level of satisfaction individuals have from their jobs. Especially since refereeing, which is done as an extra job, is not a steady source of income, administrators' attitudes and behaviours while they assign referees, their relations with other employees, and their individual performance in administration are very important for the existence and survival of their organizations within and inter-organizations (Durna, 1997).

According to the findings of the present research, female volleyball referees are more satisfied with refereeing than male referees in terms of the way their job provides for steady employment, even refereeing is not a job with fixed income.

Zelyurt et al. (2015) reported in their study that football referees have jobs, such as officer, teacher, lawyer, tradesman, and policeman. They also reported that 36.3% (n:20) of football referees did refereeing as a hobby, while 58% (n:32) did it both as a hobby and a job. According to the findings of the present research, 44.8% of the participants were public servants, 6.7% were labourers, 11.9% were self-employed and 36.6% were members of other professions, which indicate that refereeing is generally done as an extra job in Turkey.

Sport referees are the appliers of the international rules in accordance with their functions and within the limitations set by their federations. The word "referee" being the most common, there are other words used to define this job. Some other common versions are "arbiter and schlichter". Sport referees are individuals, who need to make very quick decisions, decide who is right and wrong in seconds, interpret what they see in accordance with the rules in a very short time, and most importantly, make irreversible decisions, in other words they are the judges of sports (Celik. 2004). In this context, refereeing is a job with a lot of pressure elements.

Though the pressures or potential risks that the worker can be exposed to in a shift made within 8-10 hours at a workplace are estimated in an average way. The outcomes of the referee's 90-minute-match shift can be very serious in terms of various pressure factors, which he will encounter according to the importance of the match. The observations that reveal the presence of the physical assaults and blasphemy by the fans against the referees during the game; harsh objections by the players; the threats by the club managers; the criticism on the referee decisions that have almost daily coverage in sports media. All indicate the problems, which can possibly be encountered by the

referees. (Zelyurt and Őaşmaz Atađocuđu, 2017). There is a direct relationship between these pressure factors and job satisfaction.

Compared to football referees, volleyball referees are as exposed to pressure due to factors, such as conditions of volleyball courts, security measures, spectators, and media attention. However, factors, such as wage, the chances for advancement, and doing refereeing as the primary job are also pressure elements affecting job satisfaction and working conditions. 56.7% of the volleyball referees stated that they weren't satisfied with the money they earn from refereeing (Table 2) yet 46.3% reported satisfaction due to chances for advancement (Table 3). This finding is believed to result in the findings that 33.6% of volleyball referees were satisfied with working conditions, 25.4% weren't satisfied and 24.6% were undecided (Table 4). These findings also indicate that the effects pressure elements vary by branches in sports refereeing.

The findings of the present research are as follows: General job satisfaction of volleyball referees ranges between 3.73 and neutral satisfaction level, increasing towards satisfaction level. This is a positive development for Volleyball Federation. For the institutions to survive and compete, they need to use the resources they have efficiently and increase their general performance accordingly. Average satisfaction score of referees from internal environmental conditions is 3.9200 and the average satisfaction from external environmental conditions is 3.3582. This finding indicates that referees are more satisfied with the refereeing job than they are with the opportunities provided by the federation. The federation should offer more refereeing opportunities. Employees are the most important and the most changing sources of organizations and their performance is among the most important factors affecting the success of organizations.

In this context, today's competition conditions necessitate the providing of employees with the most effective working conditions. This necessity increases the importance of providing job satisfaction among employees. Employees need to be satisfied from their jobs to exhibit high performance and work effectively. This fact raises the issues of what employees' satisfaction levels are, how they can be satisfied, and how organizations can provide a good working environment.

Some suggestions are provided below for the federation to preserve and increase volleyball referees' job satisfaction levels:

1. The federation should change its human resources policies related to the employees and the administrators of these employees to have higher achievement with the people it works with. This change should start with considering work force as a strategic advantage not as a cost to be avoided.

2. Refereeing related skills are taught at refereeing courses and in-service trainings provided by the federation. Observations on education and job training produce this consequence on the issue of skills; the requirement for highly-skilled workforce in the 21st century conflicts with the quality and the quantity of the present workforce, which has been reported many times by scientific studies. For this reason, the federation should pay extra effort in referee training (especially the male referees).

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